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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

LEA S. SORIO

Teacher - I

Basilio B. Chan Memorial Agricultura and Industrial
School

lea_sorio@deped.gov.ph

“BEHIND FEAR”

Step forward, step back,
Unfold the story of your past.
Sigh, breathe, and see how it begins,
The journey ahead, neither easy nor hard.

For the choices we take
Are not always right
A path to choose may cloud your mind,
And the things that fail to shine, you'll hide.

Blinded by earthly desires,
Swept away, you lose sight.
Like a flower that wilts in the sun
Delicate, unable to stand.

Hold your breath and think twice.
Move your feet, ignite the fire,
For tomorrow reflects who you are today.
So tell the world your story with pride.

The lessons of life, like fibers of gold,
Will shine brightly for all to see.

No perfect path,
No peerless way,
No right or wrong, just a journey on.

Don't fear mistakes,
For growth will stay.
Let the courage behind doubt guide your way
Trust it to lead, and let it be.